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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Dementia is a disease that is not a memory disorder alone but is often accompanied by other mental disorders such as language, motor skills and executive dysfunction. The person loses acquired abilities and, as a result, deterioration in daily life activities develops.

Materials and Methods: A literature search was conducted in PubMed and Web of Science databases using the keywords "Family Medicine and Dementia". Systematic reviews were included if they involved primary care or family medicine settings managing patients with dementia, and addressed topics such as the detection, diagnosis, treatment, and/or management of dementia.

Results: Dementia patients often first consult their family physicians, with 39% of patients consulting specialist physicians. Family physicians are the first physicians to observe patients with possible dementia. Five out of six studies found that the rate at which family physicians suspected dementia increased after attending a training seminar. Another study demonstrated that the duration of the training seminar had an impact on the level of knowledge regarding dementia management. Clinically, there are three stages of dementia: early, moderate and severe. In the early stage, it is important to be able to distinguish between normal aging and dementia. In the physiology of aging, a slight loss of memory can be observed, but this can be compensated when executive functions are preserved. Mild cognitive impairment is the step between normal aging and dementia. If we list the warning symptoms of dementia; memory loss, language problems, decreased reasoning ability, decreased abstract thinking, impaired perception of space and time, behavioral and personality changes, difficulty in previously performed tasks, and not being able to find things where they were put. The patient can be tested with simple questions. Personal information, current information such as whether there is important news, time and place can be questioned. Three different words are said and repeated, then another topic is mentioned, and the patient is asked to remember the three words said again.

Conclusion: For successful patient management, it is important to establish an early diagnosis while cognitive decline is still mild, to foster a good relationship between the family physician and the patient-caregiver dyad, and to enable advanced care planning. Although the patient should be referred to a neurologist for further examination and treatment, the competence of the primary care physician is very valuable in early diagnosis.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Dementia, primary care, family physicians

INTRODUCTION

Dementia is not solely characterized by memory impairment. It is frequently accompanied by other cognitive deficits, including language dysfunction, motor skill impairments, and executive function disturbances. The condition leads to a decline in previously acquired abilities, resulting in impairment in daily living activities (Visser, Vos, van Rossum, & Scheltens, 2012).

A diagnosis of dementia requires the patient to be conscious and alert, and other neuropsychiatric disorders that may present with similar clinical features must be excluded.

According to national studies conducted in Turkey, the prevalence of dementia among individuals aged 65 and older ranges between 8% and 22% (Gurvit et al., 2008; Keskinoglu et al., 2006).

Patients with dementia often initially present to primary care physicians, with only approximately 39% seeking consultation with specialist physicians (National Institutes of Health and Clinical Excellence, 2012). Family practitioners are typically the first to observe potential signs of dementia in their patients (van Hout, Vernooij-Dassen, & Stalman, 2007).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A literature search was conducted in PubMed and Web of Science databases using the keywords "Family Medicine and Dementia". Systematic reviews were included if they involved primary care or family medicine settings managing patients with dementia, and addressed topics such as the detection, diagnosis, treatment, and/or management of dementia. All full-text articles were reviewed using a standardized data extraction form. In the reviewed studies, the participation of family physicians in dementia-related training seminars was evaluated separately. The recognition rates of dementia patients by family physicians who attended these training programs were assessed at the time of their presentation to primary healthcare centers, in comparison to the overall group. Additionally, a comparison was made based on the duration of the training received. Physicians who participated in training were compared with those who did not, and further comparisons were conducted among the trained physicians according to the length of the training they received.

RESULTS

Half of the mild dementia cases were diagnosed by family physicians (Dungen et al., 2011). In a separate review, undiagnosed dementia accounted for 50–66% of all dementia cases in three primary care settings examined (Boustani et al., 2003; Eefsting et al., 1996; Olafsdóttir et al., 2000; Valcour et al., 2000). Five out of six studies found that the rate at which family physicians suspected dementia increased after attending a training seminar (Mukadam et al., 2015; Perry et al., 2011). Another study demonstrated that the duration of the training seminar had an impact on the level of knowledge regarding dementia management (Perry et al., 2011).

DISCUSSION

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is the most common cause of dementia, accounting for approximately 60–70% of cases. The prevalence of AD increases logarithmically with age, affecting 3–11% of individuals aged 65 and older, and 25–47% of those aged 85 and above (Boustani et al., 2003, 2005).

Risk factors associated with Alzheimer's disease include advanced age, a positive family history, female gender, lower educational attainment, history of head trauma, carriage of the ApoE4 allele, elevated serum cholesterol levels, and tobacco use.

In Lewy body dementia (LBD), there is a fluctuating course in terms of cognition and behavior. In addition, mild parkinsonism, where rigidity is in the foreground while tremor is in the background, REM sleep behavior disorder, where there is excessive movement during sleep, and hallucinations accompany (Boeve, 2006; Förstl et al., 1993). There is a slowdown in both cognitive areas and movements. In LBD, the loss of skills in daily activities is more pronounced than in AD.

In the early stages of frontotemporal lobar degeneration (FTLD), behavioral abnormalities such as disinhibition, apathy, or hyperactivity are frequently observed. Language disturbances may also manifest, presenting either as non-fluent (agrammatic) or fluent aphasia (Grossman, 2002; Mesulam, 1987).

In vascular cognitive impairment, the clinic varies according to the location of the ischemic lesion. Cognitive impairment is predominantly executive function. It is also frequently accompanied by gait disturbance and urinary incontinence (Mesulam, 1987). Clinically, dementia can be classified into three stages: early, moderate, and severe. Differentiating between normal aging and early-stage dementia is crucial. While mild memory decline may be observed in physiological aging, it is typically compensated for by preserved executive functions, allowing individuals to mentally plan and execute their daily tasks.

Mild cognitive impairment (MCI) represents an intermediate stage between normal aging and dementia. Individuals in this category are capable of performing daily activities independently yet report subjective memory complaints and demonstrate deficits on detailed cognitive assessments. The annual conversion rate from MCI to dementia is approximately 15%.

In the early stage of Alzheimer's disease, typically observed within the first 3–4 years, memory impairment is the primary clinical feature. Patients begin to struggle with daily tasks and often exhibit impaired insight, including forgetting that they have forgotten. Spatial disorientation and disturbances in time perception may

occur. Difficulties arise in performing calculations, managing finances, supervising household or occupational responsibilities, and operating complex appliances. While patients may still handle routine activities, impaired judgment complicates problem-solving. Comorbid depression is also common during this stage.

In the moderate stage, indoor activities become increasingly difficult and outdoor activities become nearly impossible. Language deficits impair communication, and loss of functional abilities—such as dressing—leads to growing dependence. Patients may display agitation, psychomotor hyperactivity, and delusional thoughts.

In the advanced stage, patients become entirely dependent on caregivers. Self-care abilities are lost, and gait and postural disturbances become apparent. Urinary incontinence is frequently observed (Waldemar et al., 2007).

In Alzheimer's disease (AD), symptomatic treatment options include cholinesterase inhibitors (e.g., donepezil, rivastigmine) and N-methyl-D-aspartate (NMDA) receptor antagonists such as memantine.

Regular physical exercise has been shown to reduce the risk of Alzheimer's disease, and physical activity is associated with improved cognitive performance scores (Larson et al., 2006; Weuve et al., 2004). Moreover, maintaining social engagement and participating in cognitively stimulating activities have been shown to mitigate cognitive decline in older adults (Schaie, 1996).

Risk factors for Alzheimer's disease include a positive family history, advanced age, female gender, and low educational attainment. Reversible conditions that may mimic dementia—such as depression, hypothyroidism, and vitamin B12 deficiency—should also be considered. Additionally, attention should be paid to potentially modifiable contributors to cognitive decline, such as hearing and visual impairments.

Prior to the clinical onset of dementia, patients may exhibit physical signs such as rapid weight loss, gait disturbances, and generalized motor slowing (Johnson et al., 2006; Borson et al., 2005; Buchman et al., 2008). Warning signs indicative of dementia include memory loss, language difficulties, impaired judgment, diminished abstract thinking, disorientation in time and space, changes in behavior and personality, difficulty performing previously manageable tasks, and frequently not being able to find things where you put them.

Patients who can no longer manage their medication regimen, show noticeable decline in previously competent cooking skills, have difficulty managing finances and payments, struggle with operating household devices, confuse dates, or withdraw from social activities they once attended regularly should be evaluated for dementia.

Patients can be assessed using simple screening questions targeting orientation and recent memory. These include inquiries regarding personal information, recent news events, and awareness of time and place. A three-word recall test may be utilized—examples include "table-flag-dress" or "blue-hawk-tulip." After initial repetition of the words, the patient is distracted with unrelated conversation, then asked to recall the words. Inability to recall any of the words, or recalling only one, should prompt referral for further cognitive evaluation.

Cognitive functions can be assessed using brief screening instruments in primary care settings. The Mini-Mental State Examination (MMSE) is simple and quick to administer, while the Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MoCA) provides a more complex but sensitive evaluation of cognitive deficits (Borson et al., 2005; Cummings et al., 2002; deSouza et al., 2009).

Patients with dementia may exhibit a range of behavioral symptoms, including anxiety, agitation, depression, and apathy (Craig et al., 2005; Lyketsos & Lee, 2004; Steffens et al., 2005).

For behavioral and neuropsychiatric symptoms, selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors (e.g., sertraline, citalopram, escitalopram), low-dose atypical antipsychotics (e.g., quetiapine), and sedating antidepressants such as mirtazapine or trazodone may be employed, particularly in the management of sleep disturbances.

CONCLUSION

For successful patient management, it is important to establish an early diagnosis while cognitive decline is still mild, to foster a good relationship between the family physician and the patient-caregiver dyad, and to enable advanced care planning (Tilburgs et al., 2018).

Although referral to a neurologist is necessary for advanced diagnostic evaluation, differential diagnosis, and treatment of suspected dementia, the competence of the primary care physician plays a crucial role in early detection. It is essential to recognize that dementia is not limited to memory impairment alone; behavioral and functional assessments should also be integrated into the clinical evaluation process.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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